

List of Classification Categories

For space reasons, Table 1 was omitted from a paper in which we report on the results of a systematic literature review in order to suggest a taxonomy of user feedback classification categories¹. This table details the 78 categories after merging duplicates², along with their definitions and references to the primary papers in which they were found³. These categories served as the basis for establishing our taxonomy. For the sake of clarity, we have organized them according to the same classification groups as those used in our final taxonomy.

Table 1: List of merged and grouped classification categories used in our user feedback classification taxonomy.

Category	Papers	Definition
Requirements-Relevant	P3, P37	Information that app developers are looking to identify and is potentially useful for improving the quality or user experience of apps.
Requirements-Irrelevant	P1, P3, P6, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13, P15, P16, P18, P19, P20, P24, P26, P31, P34, P35, P36, P37, P38, P39, P41	A.k.a. “Other” or “Non-Informative”. Information developers cannot get constructive information from or that does not fit any other category used by the approach.
Sentiment		
Praise	P13, P14	General appreciation with the application focusing on the whole software system
Complaint	P12, P13, P14	General dissatisfaction with the application focusing on the whole software system
Positive	P1, P11, P21, P22, P23, P32, P33, P42	Reviews associated with positive sentiments
Negative	P1, P11, P21, P22, P23, P32, P33, P42	Reviews associated with negative sentiments
User Experience		
User Experience (in General)	P8, P25	person’s perceptions and responses resulting from the use and/or anticipated use of a product, system or service
Frustration	P2, P17, P26, P27	Definition obtained from [1]
Enchantment	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from [1]
Motivation	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from [1]
Engagement	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from [1]
Affect and Emotion	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from [1]
Enjoyment & Fun	P2, P17	Definition obtained from [1]
Anticipation	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from [2]
Impact	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from [2]
User Differences	P2, P17	Definition obtained from [2]
Errors & Effectiveness	P2, P17	Definition obtained from ISO25010
Efficiency	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from ISO25010
Satisfaction	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from [3]
Trust	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from ISO25010

¹R. Santos, E. C. Groen, K. Villela, “A taxonomy for user feedback classifications,” In: P. Spoletini & P. Mäder (Eds.): *Proceedings of the 25th International Working Conference on Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality (REFSQ 2019) – Joint Proceedings of the Co-Located Events, CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 2019.

²“Learnability” appears twice in our taxonomy (under Topic and UX) due to its proximity to concepts in both groups, but is counted once.

³Bibliography of primary studies: zenodo.org/record/2546422, doi:10.5281/zenodo.2546422

Pleasure	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from ISO25010
Comfort	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from ISO25010
Utility	P27	—
Efficacy	P27	—
Hedonic Quality	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from [1]
Likeability	P2, P17	Definition obtained from [4]
Memorability	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from [3]
Learnability	P2, P11, P17, P27	ISO 25010 equivalent: “Learnability”
Support	P2, P17, P27	Definition obtained from [2]
Intention		
Presence of a Feature	P42	ISO 25010 equivalent: “Functional Completeness”
Absence of a Feature	P42	ISO 25010 equivalent: “Functional Completeness”
Advertisement	P13	Promotion of or suggestion to acquire the software
Dissuasion	P13	Advise against the acquisition of the software
Aspect Evaluation	P12	Expressing opinions for specific aspect of the app
Feature Strength	P13, P14	Reviews which identify an aspect about an existing feature that users are satisfied with
Feature Shortcoming	P13, P14, P15, P16, P26	Reviews presenting unsatisfying aspect of an existing feature
Feature Description	P9, P10, P13, P35, P36	Description of a specific feature without any objective evaluation
Job Advertisement	P13	Advertisement of a job available in the company developing the software
Information Giving	P9, P10, P13, P14, P35, P36	Explanation informing other users or developers about some aspect of the app
Rating Explanation	P25	Text reactions of the numeric star rating
Problem Report	P1, P4, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P12, P13, P14, P15, P16, P19, P20, P25, P26, P29, P31, P34, P35, P36, P38, P39, P41, P43	A.k.a. “Bug Report”. ISO 25010 equivalents: “Reliability”, “Functional Correctness”
Crashing	P26	Comments on frequent app crashes; ISO 25010 equivalent: “Fault Tolerance”
Network Issue	P26	Comments on problems related to the network during use of the software, e.g. lags
Unexpected Behavior	P26	Comment on an unexpected behaviour or failure; ISO 25010 equivalents: “Fault Tolerance”, “Recoverability”
Feature Request	P1, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P14, P15, P16, P18, P20, P24, P25, P26, P28, P29, P31, P32, P34, P35, P36, P40, P41	Users’ suggestion on functionality enhancement. Suggestions, improvements, requests to add/modify/bring back/remove features.
Enhance Feature	P1, P14	Suggestions to improve features available in the product
New Feature	P13, P38, P39,	Suggestions for features not yet available in the product
Non-Functional Request	P5, P34	Request such as design and content related issues.

Information Seeking	P9, P10, P13, P35, P36	Attempt to obtain information or help from other users or developers
Topic		
Protection Security	P4, P9, P10, P27, P35, P36	ISO 25010 equivalent: "Security"
Privacy	P4, P38	Reviews about security.
Resources	P4, P26	Reviews about privacy.
Memory	P4, P9, P10, P26, P35, P36	ISO 25010 equivalent: "Resource Utilization"
Battery	P4	Discusses memory or storage usage by the software.
Portability	P4, P20	Discusses battery usage by the software.
Device	P4, P9, P10, P13, P24, P26, P35, P36, P40	ISO 25010 equivalent: "Portability"
Hardware	P4	Mentions a specific Operating system and possibly its version
OS Version	P4, P13	Mentions a specific hardware component
Software	P4	Mentions a specific mobile phone device model
Usability	P13	Mentions a specific software component needed to run the product software
Operability	P2, P4, P11, P17, P24, P26, P27, P38, P40	ISO 25010 equivalent: "Usability"
Learnability	P11	ISO 25010 equivalent: "Operability"
Reliability	P2, P11, P17, P27	ISO 25010 equivalent: "Learnability"
Performance	P11, P24, P40	ISO 25010 equivalent: "Reliability"
User Interface	P4, P24, P26, P38, P40	ISO 25010 equivalent: "Performance Efficiency", specifically "Time Behaviour"
Accessibility Support	P2, P4, P9, P10, P11, P17, P26, P27, P35, P36,	ISO 25010 equivalent: "User Interface Aesthetics"
Social Interaction	P27	ISO 25010 equivalent: "Accessibility"
Download	P13	Personal issues that arise due to the use of the software
Company	P9, P10, P35, P36	ISO 25010 equivalent: "Installability"
Service	P9, P10, P35, P36	Feedback related to the company/team which develops the app
Price	P13	Comment on the service provided by the software
Licensing	P4, P9, P10, P13, P26, P35, P36,	Discussion of software price
Compliance Issue	P4	Statements discussing the software licensing model
Other Product	P13	Dispute over certain terms of agreement or regulations
Software Extension	P13	Mentions of aspects of a similar product.
Content-Related	P13	Description of (planned) extensions of the software
Updates or Versions	P9, P10, P13, P35, P36	Comment about content that was created or is available through the software
Whole App	P9, P10, P26, P35, P36	Reviews mentioning specific versions or the update process of the app
	P9, P10, P35, P36	Reviews related to the entire app without further explanation, e.g., generic crash reports, ratings, or general feedback

References

- [1] J. A.argas-Avila and K. Hornbæk, “Old wine in new bottles or novel challenges? A critical analysis of empirical studies of user experience,” in *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)*, 2011, pp. 2689–2698.
- [2] P. Ketola and V. Roto, “Exploring user experience measurement needs,” in *Proceedings of the 5th COST294-MAUSE Open Workshop on Valid Useful User Experience Measurement (VUUM)*, 2008, pp. 23–26.
- [3] J. Nielsen, *Usability Engineering*. San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann, 1993.
- [4] N. Bevan, “Classifying and selecting UX and usability measures,” *Proceedings of the 5th COST294-MAUSE Open Workshop on Valid Useful User Experience Measurement (VUUM)*, pp. 13–18, 2008.